

Gender-Responsive Pedagogies in AI-Powered Learning Environments

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Abstract. How can we build inclusive and equitable learning environments in the AI era? As AI adoption in education accelerates, it reshapes the organization of educational systems, pedagogical approaches, and the use of learning tools. UNESCO's AI competency frameworks for teachers and learners emphasize the need for AI tools that prioritize human-centered principles, equity, inclusivity, and ethical governance. Despite AI's potential benefits in teaching and learning, systemic gender inequalities and gaps remain: women represent only a fraction of AI researchers, faculty, and leaders in AI-related positions, and a gender gap in generative AI usage has already been observed.

These disparities highlight two major challenges: first, ensuring that pedagogies and educational tools do not perpetuate biases or widen existing gaps; and second, fostering AI literacy and AI skills for women and underrepresented groups. How can we develop gender-responsive standards and frameworks that specifically consider gender implications in creating learning content and learning solutions that use generative AI? Applying the United Nations Gender Equality Markers (GEM) offers a roadmap for integrating gender considerations across the learning design and the AI powered learning technologies lifecycle—from initial design and data collection to development, implementation and evaluation. By incorporating gender-responsive principles and leveraging practical tools and checklists, stakeholders can work collectively to create educational and technological solutions that reflect varied experiences and diversity. This workshop will bring together learning design and gender experts to explore potential futures,

fostering guidelines and methodologies for gender mainstreaming in AI-powered learning environments.

Keywords: Gender-responsive pedagogies, Inclusion, AI Gender gap in education.

1 Introduction

The challenge is no longer about whether to adopt AI, but rather how to do so in a way that aligns with human-centered principles. UNESCO’s AI competency frameworks [1] [2] call for the development of AI skills and tools that prioritize equity, inclusivity, and ethical governance. What is the role of all education stakeholders in harnessing AI for public good without exacerbating inequalities?

In the broader landscape of science and R&D, women make up just 29% of researchers, a proportion that drops to 12% in specialized AI research roles. Within academia, only 16% of AI faculty positions are held by women, and in the wider AI sector, 30% of professionals identify as women. This disparity becomes even more pronounced at senior levels: merely 18% of C-suite roles in AI startups are occupied by women. [3] If there is a significant gender gap in who is shaping technologies, a gender gap in generative AI usage has also been established [4]. The limited participation of women in generative AI use will cause systems to rely on data that insufficiently reflect women’s preferences and needs, ultimately reinforcing existing gender inequalities in technology adoption.

In May 2021, the Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education stated the following: “UNESCO Member States INVITE the Director-General of UNESCO to seek to implement the following actions: Establish an ‘AI for Education’ platform to act as a clearinghouse for open-source AI courses, AI tools, examples of AI in education policies (...) and making open-source AI resources and courses accessible to all.”[5] If teaching and learning increasingly rely on AI technologies, how do we ensure that these new AI-powered learning environment remain accessible to all? How can we create gender-inclusive learning platforms and tools—built by diverse teams, aware of potential bias, and informed by a wide range of lived experiences, perspectives, and identities—that follow a gender-responsive [6] approach at every stage (from design, data collection, development, implementation and evaluation [7])?

Furthermore, how might we develop the necessary competencies among stakeholders—designers, coders, educators, and technologists—to align education and technology development with UNESCO’s gender-responsive pedagogies [8]?

We will examine strategies for integrating gender considerations across all phases of the design cycle. Taking as a starting point the United Nations Gender Equality Markers (GEM), reflecting on how gender-responsive approaches can be embedded within AI development. This workshop will explore practical recommendations for creating more

equitable learning environments. This includes the use of examples, tools, and checklists that promote gender-transformative approaches and foster more inclusive online pedagogies—ultimately shaping an edtech ecosystem that reflects the principles of gender equality, equity and inclusion [9].

2 Proposed agenda (3 hours)

(15 min) Introduction to the workshop objectives (Ella Hamonic and Patrice Torcivia Prusko)

2.1 Gender-responsive learning frameworks: from learning design to education technology development

(15 minutes) Presentation: Patrice Torcivia Prusko, Harvard Graduate School of Education

How might we design gender inclusive platforms and tools that have diverse teams, are cognizant of potential bias, reflect a wide range of lived experiences, perspectives and identities and take a design justice approach [10], [11], [12] through the entire cycle from ideation, data collection, prototype, gathering feedback and implementation. How might we design competencies and build them in stakeholders, designers, coders, educators, and technologists with a focus on alignment with UNESCO gender responsive pedagogies?

2.2 Mainstreaming Gender in Online TVET Programme: Transforming Learning Design with Gender-Responsive Pedagogy

(15 minutes) Presentation: Fabricia Devignes, IIEP UNESCO Paris with the contribution of Margherita Boccalatte and Khalil Bahloul IIEP UNESCO Dakar

This presentation will explore mainstreaming gender in an online Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programme by transforming learning design practices. It examines strategies for integrating gender considerations across all phases of the training cycle, from planning and analysis to design, development, implementation, and evaluation. Taking as a starting point the United Nations Gender Equality Markers (GEM), it will provide insights how gender-responsive approaches can be embedded within an online TVET program [13]. This includes adapting curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment to promote gender equality. The presentation will focus particularly on the redesign of a TVET management training program implemented in by IIEP-UNESCO in Dakar.

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2.3 Build inclusive and sustainable AI data, tools, services, and platforms with gender lenses

(15 minutes) Presentation: Siddhi Gupta, AI inclusive Lab (University of Utrecht) & Co-Lead Creative AI Cluster, Inclusive AI Lab and Assistant Professor, Srishti Manipal Institute of Art, Design and Technology

This presentation proposes a framework for understanding technology-mediated learning, grounded in fieldwork conducted in India following the pandemic. It highlights strategies for designing inclusive and sustainable AI-driven data, tools, services, and platforms that center the needs, concerns, experiences, and aspirations of chronically marginalized communities—particularly in the Global South. By examining the interconnected elements of learning—users, tools, content, spaces, communication, and context—the presentation offers critical provocations for designers committed to creating equitable and meaningful learning experiences.

Break 10 minutes

2.4 Applying frameworks to scenarios

(1 hour in teams)

Group 1: Designing a new online course with gender lenses

Group 2: Building a new learning application using AI (i.e: introducing an AI chatbot into my course) implementing gender-responsive prompting.

Group 3: Use debiased LLM: where to start?

Break 10 min

2.5 Discussion and Future thinking

(30 minutes) Discussion

(10 minutes) Wrap-up and survey

3 Expected number of participants

15-25 people

4 Technical needs

Room layout designed to facilitate group work in teams of five, with Post-it notes, three flipcharts, and markers provided.

References

1. Miao, F., Cukurova, M.: AI competency framework for teachers, UNESCO (2024) <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391104>, last accessed 2025/04/03
2. Miao, F., Shiohira, K., Lao, N: AI competency framework for students UNESCO (2024) <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391105>, last accessed 2025/04/03
3. UNESCO, Women for Ethical AI: outlook study on artificial intelligence and gender <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391719>, last accessed 2025/04/03
4. Nicholas, O., Delecourt, S., Cranney, K., and Koning R., Global Evidence on Gender Gaps and Generative AI: Harvard Business School Working Paper, No. 25-023 (October 2024 revised January 2025)
5. UNESCO, Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education (2021) <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000368303>, last accessed 2025/04/03
6. Cotón, X., Urgoiti Aristegui, A., IDB, Online Courses: Gender and Diversity Mainstreaming Guidelines, IDB, (2021) <https://publications.iadb.org/en/online-courses-gender-and-diversity-mainstreaming-guidelines> last accessed 2025/04/03
7. United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR), Mainstreaming gender in the training cycle integrating a gender perspective into training design. [https://unitar.org/sites/default/files/me-
dia/file/UNITAR%20Mainstreaming%20Gender%20in%20the%20Training%20Cycle.pdf](https://unitar.org/sites/default/files/media/file/UNITAR%20Mainstreaming%20Gender%20in%20the%20Training%20Cycle.pdf) (2022), last accessed 2025/04/03
8. UNESCO, From access to empowerment: operational tools to advance gender equality in and through education, (2021) <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380259>, last accessed 2025/04/03
9. International Development Research Centre, Gender Equality in and through Education: A Research Synthesis. Ottawa, Canada. (2024) <https://www.gpekix.org/knowledge-repository/gender-equality-and-through-education-research-synthesis> last accessed 2025/04/03
10. Silverman, S., Desired results: Tensions between Backward Design and Feminist Pedagogy, (2024) <https://sarahemilysilverman.com/2024/04/01/desired-results-tensions-between-backward-design-and-feminist-pedagogy/> last accessed 2025/04/03
11. Smith, E., Hyder. M, Incorporating Feminist Pedagogy Into Your Courses, <https://learning.nd.edu/resource-library/incorporating-feminist-pedagogy-into-your-courses/> last accessed 2025/04/03
12. Thonu Howard,J., Romero-Hall, E., Daniel, C., Bond, N., Newman, L., Feminist Pedagogy for Teaching Online, A Digital Guide, in Distance Education, AU Press, to be published, <https://feminists-teach-online.tulane.edu/> last accessed 2025/04/03
13. UNESCO, Gender responsive and inclusive TEVET training course: instructors' handbook (2019) <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000369087> last accessed 2025/04/03